

Supplementary information of the paper: Impact of a block structure on the Lotka-Volterra model.

Appendix A. Stieltjes transform

We provide some reminders regarding Stieltjes transforms, a central element of proofs in random matrix theory. We denote by

$$\mathbb{C}^+ := \{z \in \mathbb{C} : \text{Im}(z) > 0\}$$

the upper half of the complex plane.

Definition A.1 (Stieltjes transform). Let $\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R})$ be a probability measure. The Stieltjes transform of ν , denoted by $g_\nu : \mathbb{C}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, is defined by

$$g_\nu(z) = \int \frac{1}{\lambda - z} \nu(d\lambda), z \in \mathbb{C}^+.$$

Remark 10. Let ν_X be the empirical measure of the eigenvalues $\lambda_1(X), \dots, \lambda_n(X)$ of the symmetric matrix $X \in \mathcal{M}_n(\mathbb{C})$ define by

$$\nu_X := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \delta_{\lambda_k(X)}.$$

then the associated Stieltjes transform is given by

$$g_{\nu_X}(z) = \int \frac{1}{\lambda - z} \nu_X(d\lambda) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\lambda_i - z} = \frac{1}{n} \text{Tr} \left((X - zI)^{-1} \right),$$

where $Q = (X - zI)^{-1}$ is the resolvent of the matrix X and $\text{Tr}(Q)$ is the trace of matrix Q .

Proposition A.2 (Stieltjes inversion). Let g_ν the Stieltjes transform of the measure ν of finite mass $\nu(\mathbb{R})$. If $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\nu(\{a\}) = \nu(\{b\}) = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(a, b) &= \frac{1}{\pi} \lim_{y \rightarrow 0^+} \text{Im} \int_a^b g_\nu(x + iy) dx, \\ \forall x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad \nu(\{x\}) &= \frac{1}{\pi} \lim_{y \rightarrow 0^+} \text{Im}(g_\nu(x + iy)). \end{aligned}$$

Appendix B. Numerical methods

B.1. Methods for validating heuristics 1

To verify the system of equations of heuristics 1, the simulations on the properties of surviving species are performed in two distinct methods (see Fig. 3). On the one hand, we use a standard solver (cf. `scipy.optimize`) to find the theoretical solutions by finding a local minimum of the system of equations (a modification of the Powell hybrid method). On the other hand, we simulate a large number of matrix B , each corresponding to an experiment, and we resolve the associated LCP problem using the Lemke's algorithm (see the `lemkelcp` package Lamperski, 2019). The empirical solutions are computed using a Monte Carlo experiment, i.e. we use the LCP solution to compute the properties of the surviving species and we make an average over the ensemble of experiments. As a baseline, the dynamics of Lotka-Volterra are achieved by a Runge-Kutta method of order 4 (RK4) implemented in the code.

B.2. Spectrum: a computer based approach.

Theorem 2.3 only provides sufficient conditions for the existence of a unique stable equilibrium and is based on the rough asymptotic upper bound estimation $\Sigma = 2 \|S\|_\infty^{1/2}$. We can assess the sharpness of this bound by comparing it to the limiting spectrum of matrix H , which can be plotted via numerical simulations. An efficient way to compute numerically the spectrum of the matrix H comes from the system of non linear equations (12).

Starting from the QVE equations (12) associated to the matrix H , the system takes the simpler form

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{1}{m(z)} &= z + 2\beta_1 s_{11}^2 m(z) + \beta_2 (s_{12}^2 + s_{21}^2) \check{m}(z) \\ -\frac{1}{\check{m}(z)} &= z + \beta_1 (s_{12}^2 + s_{21}^2) m(z) + 2\beta_2 s_{22}^2 \check{m}(z) \end{cases},$$

where for $k \in \mathcal{I}_1$, $m_k(z) = m(z)$ and for $k \in \mathcal{I}_2$, $m_k(z) = \check{m}(z)$. One can indeed check that with m and \check{m} defined as above, then

$$(28) \quad \mathbf{m}^\top = \underbrace{[m, \dots, m]}_{n_1}, \underbrace{[\check{m}, \dots, \check{m}]}_{n_2}$$

satisfies the QVE equations (12); here $n_1 = |\mathcal{I}_1|$ and $n_2 = |\mathcal{I}_2|$. Since this solution \mathbf{m} is unique, \mathbf{m} is necessarily given by the simplified form (28).

All the knowledge of equation (12) hence relies on functions $m(z)$ and $\check{m}(z)$. Then, using the RMT results developed in (Ajanki et al., 2017), the resolvent G of the symmetric matrix H can be approximated by

$$G(z) = (H - zI)^{-1} \simeq \text{diag}(m(z)\mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{I}_1}^\top, \check{m}(z)\mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{I}_2}^\top).$$

From Remark 10, the trace of the resolvent is equal to the Stieltjes transform

$$g(z) = \frac{1}{n} \text{Tr}(G) \simeq \beta_1 m(z) + \beta_2 \check{m}(z)$$

of the spectral measure. Finally, the spectral density can be obtained using the Stieltjes inversion formula, see Prop. A.2. The spectral density of the matrix H can be computed numerically by an iterative scheme. The initial condition of the two measurements (m, \check{m}) is $m_0 = \check{m}_0 = -\frac{1}{z}$. Then, the iterative scheme

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{1}{m_p} &= z + 2\beta_1 s_{11}^2 m_{p-1} + \beta_2 (s_{12}^2 + s_{21}^2) \check{m}_{p-1} \\ -\frac{1}{\check{m}_p} &= z + \beta_1 (s_{12}^2 + s_{21}^2) m_{p-1} + 2\beta_2 s_{22}^2 \check{m}_{p-1} \end{cases},$$

converge to $m_\infty = \lim_{p \rightarrow +\infty} m_p$ and $\check{m}_\infty = \lim_{p \rightarrow +\infty} \check{m}_p$. The last step consists in using the Stieltjes inversion formule, see Prop.A.2.

Remark 11. To handle the Stieltjes inversion (Prop.A.2) numerically, it is similar as starting with $z = x + \epsilon i$, $\epsilon \approx 10^{-3}$.

In Fig. 12, we present the numerical estimation of the spectral density for different types of interactions of the matrix H .

Appendix C. Remaining computations

C.1. Moments of \check{Z}_k

We compute hereafter the conditional variance of $\check{Z}_k = (B\mathbf{x}^*)_k$ with respect to \mathbf{x}^* . It should be noted that the assumption of independence between (x_k^*) and (B_{kl}) is a strong one, although it is likely to be true asymptotically, supported by the chaos hypothesis.

$$(a) \beta = [1/2, 1/2], \mathbf{s} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{2} \\ 1/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{2} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$(b) \beta = [1/2, 1/2], \mathbf{s} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/2 & 1 \\ 1 & 1/8 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$(c) \beta = [1/2, 1/2], \mathbf{s} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1/2 \\ 1/8 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$(d) \beta = [3/4, 1/4], \mathbf{s} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/3 & 1/5 \\ 1 & 1/2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Figure 12 – Spectrum (histogram) of the Hermitian random matrix H ($n = 1000$), conditions on (β, \mathbf{s}) are given in each panel. The numerical approach is used to compute the solid line spectrum distribution. An upper bound for the largest eigenvalue of H , given by $2 \|\mathbf{S}\|_{\infty}^{1/2}$, is denoted by the dashed vertical line.

We rely on the following identities $\forall k \in \mathcal{I}_i, \forall \ell \in \mathcal{I}_j$ and $\forall o \in \mathcal{I}_q$:

$$\mathbb{E}B_{kl} = 0 \quad , \quad \mathbb{E}(B_{kl}^2) = \frac{s_{ij}^2}{n} \quad , \quad \mathbb{E}B_{kl}B_{ko} = 0 \quad (\ell \neq o).$$

We first compute the conditional mean:

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{I}_i, \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}^*}(\check{Z}_k) = \sum_{\ell \in [n]} \mathbb{E}(B_{kl})x_{\ell}^* = \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{S}_1} \mathbb{E}(B_{kl})x_{\ell}^* + \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{S}_2} \mathbb{E}(B_{kl})x_{\ell}^* = 0.$$

We now compute the second moment:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall k \in \mathcal{I}_i, \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}^*}(\check{Z}_k^2) &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}^*} \left(\sum_{\ell \in [n]} B_{kl}x_{\ell}^* \right)^2 = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}^*} \sum_{\ell, o \in [n]} B_{kl}B_{ko}x_{\ell}^*x_o^*, \\ &= \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{S}_1 \cup \mathcal{S}_2} \mathbb{E}(B_{kl}^2)x_{\ell}^{*2} + \sum_{\ell \neq o} \mathbb{E}(B_{kl}B_{ko})x_{\ell}^*x_o^*, \\ &= \frac{s_{i1}^2}{n} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{S}_1} x_{\ell}^{*2} + \frac{s_{i2}^2}{n} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{S}_2} x_{\ell}^{*2}, \\ &= \beta_1 \hat{p}_1 \hat{\sigma}_1^2 s_{i1}^2 + \beta_2 \hat{p}_2 \hat{\sigma}_2^2 s_{i2}^2, \end{aligned}$$

We can now compute the variance:

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{I}_i, \text{Var}_{\mathbf{x}^*}(\check{Z}_k) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}^*}(\check{Z}_k^2) - (\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}^*}\check{Z}_k)^2 = \beta_1 \hat{p}_1 \hat{\sigma}_1^2 s_{i1}^2 + \beta_2 \hat{p}_2 \hat{\sigma}_2^2 s_{i2}^2.$$

C.2. Details of heuristics of the mean

Our starting point is the following generic representation of an abundance at equilibrium (either of a surviving or vanishing species) in the case $k \in \mathcal{S}_i$:

$$x_k^* = (1 + \Delta_i^* Z_k) \mathbf{1}_{\{Z_k > \delta_i^*\}} = \mathbf{1}_{\{Z_k > \delta_i^*\}} + (\Delta_i^* Z_k) \mathbf{1}_{\{Z_k > \delta_i^*\}}.$$

Summing over \mathcal{S}_i and normalizing,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{|\mathcal{S}_i|} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{S}_i} x_k^* &= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{S}_i|} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{S}_i} \mathbf{1}_{\{Z_k > \delta_i^*\}} + \Delta_i^* \frac{1}{|\mathcal{S}_i|} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{S}_i} Z_k \mathbf{1}_{\{Z_k > \delta_i^*\}}, \\ \hat{m}_i &\stackrel{(a)}{=} 1 + \Delta_i^* \frac{|\mathcal{I}_i|}{|\mathcal{S}_i|} \frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}_i|} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{I}_i} Z_k \mathbf{1}_{\{Z_k > \delta_i^*\}}, \\ \hat{m}_i &\stackrel{(b)}{\simeq} 1 + \Delta_i^* \frac{1}{\mathbb{P}(Z > \delta_i^*)} \mathbb{E}(Z \mathbf{1}_{\{Z > \delta_i^*\}}), \\ \hat{m}_i &\simeq 1 + \Delta_i^* \mathbb{E}(Z | Z > \delta_i^*). \end{aligned}$$

where (a) follows from the fact that $|\mathcal{S}_i| = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{S}_i} \mathbf{1}_{\{Z_k > \delta_i^*\}}$ (by definition of \mathcal{S}_i), (b) from the law of large numbers $\frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}_i|} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{I}_i} Z_k \mathbf{1}_{\{Z_k > \delta_i^*\}} \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E} Z \mathbf{1}_{\{Z > \delta_i^*\}}$ and $\frac{|\mathcal{S}_i|}{|\mathcal{I}_i|} \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{P}(Z > \delta_i^*)$ with $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. It remains to replace \hat{m}_i by its limit m_i^* to obtain the heuristics of the mean:

$$\begin{aligned} m_1^* &= 1 + \Delta_1^* \mathbb{E}(Z | Z > \delta_1^*), \\ m_2^* &= 1 + \Delta_2^* \mathbb{E}(Z | Z > \delta_2^*). \end{aligned}$$

C.3. Density of the distribution of the surviving species.

Assume that $x^* > 0$, and let $f = \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a bounded continuous test function, then $\forall k \in \mathcal{S}_i$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}f(x_k^*) &= \mathbf{E} \left[f(1 + \Delta_i^* Z_k) \mid Z_k > \delta_i^* \right], \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(1 + \Delta_i^* u) \frac{\mathbf{1}_{\{u > \delta_i^*\}}}{1 - \Phi(\delta_i^*)} \frac{e^{-\frac{u^2}{2}}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} du, \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} f(y) e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{y}{\Delta_i^*} + \delta_i^* \right)^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi} \Phi(-\delta_i^*) \Delta_i^*} dy, \end{aligned}$$

hence the density of x_k^* , $\forall k \in \mathcal{S}_i$.

Appendix D. Sketch of proof of Theorem 4.1

The first step consists in decomposing the equilibrium \mathbf{x}^* :

$$\begin{aligned} x_k^* &= e_k^\top \mathbf{x}^* = e_k^\top (I - B)^{-1} \mathbf{1} = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} e_k^\top B^\ell \mathbf{1} = 1 + e_k^\top B \mathbf{1} + e_k^\top B^2 (I - B)^{-1} \mathbf{1}, \\ &= 1 + Z_k + R_k, \end{aligned}$$

where $Z_k = \sum_{\ell=1}^n B_{k\ell}$, $\forall k \in [n]$.

One can prove that $\forall k \in [n]$, R_k is a negligible term if n is sufficiently large. From a technical point, it relies on Gaussian concentration of Lipschitz functionals and we are confident that the

techniques applied in (Bizeul and Najim, 2021) will succeed in handling R_k . However, this part of the proof is not been treated here since we want to stick a concise argumentation of the proof which gives the reader information about the critical bound of the feasibility threshold.

The feasibility of the two communities is studied independently. Using Gaussian addition properties, a simpler form of Z_k is first deduced. Consider a family $(\check{Z}_k)_{k \in [n]}$ of i.i.d. random variables $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } k \in \mathcal{I}_1, Z_k &= \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I}_1} B_{k\ell} + \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I}_2} B_{k\ell}, \\ &\sim \mathcal{N}\left(0, \beta_1 s_{11}^2\right) + \mathcal{N}\left(0, \beta_2 s_{12}^2\right), \\ &\sim \sqrt{\beta_1 s_{11}^2 + \beta_2 s_{12}^2} \check{Z}_k. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly

$$\text{if } k \in \mathcal{I}_2, Z_k \sim \sqrt{\beta_1 s_{21}^2 + \beta_2 s_{22}^2} \check{Z}_k.$$

Given $\beta = (\beta_1, \beta_2)$, conditions on the matrix \mathbf{s} are inferred to have:

$$(29) \quad \mathbb{P}\left(\min_{k \in [n]} x_k > 0\right) = 1 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \mathbb{P}\left(\min_{k \in [n]} Z_k > -1\right) = 1.$$

In order to compute a tractable form of $\min_{k \in [n]} Z_k$, an additional approximation is made. Since $(\check{Z}_k)_{k \in [n]}$ is a family of i.i.d. random variables $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, using standard extreme value theory of Gaussian random variables (see Leadbetter *et al.* (Leadbetter et al., 1983)), if n is large enough

$$(30) \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad \min_{k \in \mathcal{I}_i} \check{Z}_k \sim -\sqrt{2 \log(\beta_i n)} \approx -\sqrt{2 \log(n)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{k \in [n]} Z_k &= \min\left(\sqrt{\beta_1 s_{11}^2 + \beta_2 s_{12}^2} \min_{k \in \mathcal{I}_1} \check{Z}_k, \sqrt{\beta_1 s_{21}^2 + \beta_2 s_{22}^2} \min_{k \in \mathcal{I}_2} \check{Z}_k\right), \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{\simeq} \min\left(\sqrt{\beta_1 s_{11}^2 + \beta_2 s_{12}^2} \left(-\sqrt{2 \log(n)}\right), \sqrt{\beta_1 s_{21}^2 + \beta_2 s_{22}^2} \left(-\sqrt{2 \log(n)}\right)\right), \\ &= \min\left(-\sqrt{2\beta_1 s_{11}^2 \log(n) + 2\beta_2 s_{12}^2 \log(n)}, -\sqrt{2\beta_1 s_{21}^2 \log(n) + 2\beta_2 s_{22}^2 \log(n)}\right), \\ &= -\max\left(\sqrt{2\beta_1 s_{11}^2 \log(n) + 2\beta_2 s_{12}^2 \log(n)}, \sqrt{2\beta_1 s_{21}^2 \log(n) + 2\beta_2 s_{22}^2 \log(n)}\right). \end{aligned}$$

where (a) comes from the approximation (30). The condition $\min_{k \in [n]} Z_k > -1$ asymptotically boils down to

$$\begin{aligned} &\max\left(\sqrt{2\beta_1 s_{11}^2 \log(n) + 2\beta_2 s_{12}^2 \log(n)}, \sqrt{2\beta_1 s_{21}^2 \log(n) + 2\beta_2 s_{22}^2 \log(n)}\right) < 1, \\ \Leftrightarrow &\max\left(2\beta_1 s_{11}^2 \log(n) + 2\beta_2 s_{12}^2 \log(n), 2\beta_1 s_{21}^2 \log(n) + 2\beta_2 s_{22}^2 \log(n)\right) < 1, \\ \Leftrightarrow &\max\left(\beta_1 s_{11}^2 + \beta_2 s_{12}^2, \beta_1 s_{21}^2 + \beta_2 s_{22}^2\right) < \frac{1}{2 \log(n)}, \\ \Leftrightarrow &\left\|(\mathbf{s}_n \circ \mathbf{s}_n) \boldsymbol{\beta}^\top\right\|_\infty < \frac{1}{2 \log(n)} := (s_n^*)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Appendix E. Extension to the b -blocks model

E.1. Interaction matrix with b communities

Within the framework of b communities, the matrix $B = (B_{kl})_{n,n}$ is defined as

$$(31) \quad B = V\mathbf{s}V^\top \circ \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}A,$$

where

$$V \in \mathcal{M}_{n \times b}, \quad V = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{I}_1} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{I}_2} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & \mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{I}_b} \end{pmatrix}, \quad A = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & \cdots & A_{1b} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{b1} & \cdots & A_{bb} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{s} = \begin{pmatrix} s_{11} & \cdots & s_{1b} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ s_{b1} & \cdots & s_{bb} \end{pmatrix},$$

where $\mathcal{I}_1 = [n_1]$, $\mathcal{I}_2 = \{n_1 + 1, \dots, n_1 + n_2\}, \dots, \mathcal{I}_b = \{n_1 + \dots + n_{b-1} + 1, \dots, n\}$ the subset of $[n]$ of size $|\mathcal{I}_i| := n_i$ matching the index of species belonging to community i and $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_b)$ with $\forall i \in [b]$, $\beta_i = n_i/n$ and $\sum_{i=1}^b \beta_i = 1$. The random matrix A_{ij} is non-Hermitian of size $|\mathcal{I}_i| \times |\mathcal{I}_j|$ with standard Gaussian entries i.e. $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. Recall that $\mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{I}_i}$ be the element-wise vector of 1 with size $|\mathcal{I}_i|$.

E.2. Existence of a unique equilibrium

Let H be the symmetric matrix

$$H = B + B^\top = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \begin{pmatrix} H_{11} & \cdots & H_{1b} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ H_{b1} & \cdots & H_{bb} \end{pmatrix},$$

where $\forall i, j \in [b]$, H_{ij} is a matrix of size $|\mathcal{I}_i| \times |\mathcal{I}_j|$ and each off-diagonal entries follow a Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, s_{ij}^2 + s_{ji}^2)$. The QVE associated to the matrix H is decomposed as

$$k \in \mathcal{I}_i, \quad -\frac{1}{m_k(z)} = z + \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I}_j} \frac{1}{n} (s_{ij}^2 + s_{ji}^2) m_\ell(z).$$

Given $\mathbf{m}(z) = (m_1(z), \dots, m_n(z))$, denote by $1/\mathbf{m}(z) = (1/m_1(z), \dots, 1/m_n(z))$ and $S = \frac{1}{n} V(\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{s}^\top)V^\top$ the QVE can be written in the standard form

$$(32) \quad -\frac{1}{\mathbf{m}(z)} = z + S\mathbf{m}(z).$$

Following the same arguments as in Theorem 2.3 and relying on Theorem 2.2, given the particular shape of the matrix S , computing its norm is equivalent to computing the norm of a matrix of size b

$$\|S\|_\infty = \left\| \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) \left((\mathbf{s} \circ \mathbf{s}) + (\mathbf{s} \circ \mathbf{s})^\top \right) \right\|_\infty.$$

E.3. Surviving species

Heuristics 3. Let \mathbf{s} be the $b \times b$ matrix of interaction strengths and assume that the condition of Theorem 2.3 holds, then the following system of $2b$ equations and $2b$ unknowns $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_b)$, $\boldsymbol{\sigma} =$

$(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_b)$

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i \in [b], p_i &= 1 - \Phi(\delta_i), \\ \forall i \in [b], (\sigma_i)^2 &= 1 + 2\Delta_i \mathbb{E}(Z|Z > \delta_i) + \Delta_i^2 \mathbb{E}(Z^2|Z > \delta_i), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\Delta_i = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^b p_j(\sigma_j)^2 \beta_j s_{ij}^2}; \delta_i = -\frac{1}{\Delta_i},$$

admits a unique solution $(\mathbf{p}^*, \boldsymbol{\sigma}^*)$ and $\forall i \in [b]$

$$\hat{p}_i \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{a.s.} p_i^* \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{\sigma}_i \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{a.s.} \sigma_i^*.$$

E.4. Distribution of the surviving species

Let \mathbf{s} be the $b \times b$ matrix of interaction strengths and assume that the condition of Theorem 2.3 holds. Let \mathbf{x}^* the solution of (9) and $(\mathbf{p}^*, \boldsymbol{\sigma}^*)$ the solution of the heuristic 3. Recall the definition of Δ_i , δ_i and denote by $\delta_i^* = \delta_i(p_i^*, \sigma_i^*)$. Let $x_k^* > 0$ a positive component of \mathbf{x}^* belonging to the community i , then:

$$\mathcal{L}(x_k^*) \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{} \mathcal{L}\left(1 + \Delta_i^* Z \mid Z > \delta_i^*\right),$$

where $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. Otherwise stated, asymptotically $\forall k \in \mathcal{S}_i$, x_k^* admits the following density

$$(33) \quad f_k(y) = \frac{\mathbf{1}_{\{y > 0\}}}{\Phi(-\delta_i^*)} \frac{1}{\Delta_i^* \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{y}{\Delta_i^*} + \delta_i^*\right)^2\right\}.$$

E.5. Feasibility

We consider a growing scaling matrix

$$\mathbf{s}_n \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{} \mathbf{0} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \forall i, j \in \{1, b\}, s_{ij} \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{} 0.$$

Let B_n a matrix defined by

$$(34) \quad B_n = V \mathbf{s}_n V^\top \circ \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} A.$$

The spectral radius of $\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} A$ a.s. converges to 1 (circular law). So as long as \mathbf{s}_n is close to zero, the matrix $I - B_n$ is eventually invertible.

Recall the problem which admits a unique solution defined by

$$(35) \quad \mathbf{x}^* = \mathbf{1} + B \mathbf{x}^* \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{x}^* = (I - B)^{-1} \mathbf{1},$$

Theorem E.1 (Co-feasibility for the b -blocks model). Assume that matrix B_n is defined by the b -blocks model (34). Let $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_b)$, $\sum_{i=1}^b \beta_i = 1$ represents the proportion of each community. Let $\mathbf{s}_n \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{} \mathbf{0}$ and denote by $s_n^* = 1/\sqrt{2 \log n}$. Let $\mathbf{x}_n = (x_k)_{k \in [n]}$ be the solution of (35).

(1) If there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that eventually $\|(\mathbf{s}_n \circ \mathbf{s}_n) \boldsymbol{\beta}^\top\|_\infty \geq (1 + \varepsilon)(s_n^*)^2$ then

$$\mathbb{P}\left\{\min_{k \in [n]} x_k > 0\right\} \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{} 0.$$

(2) If there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that eventually $\|(\mathbf{s}_n \circ \mathbf{s}_n)\beta^\top\|_\infty \leq (1 - \varepsilon)(s_n^*)^2$ then

$$\mathbb{P}\left\{\min_{k \in [n]} x_k > 0\right\} \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 1.$$

Sketch of proof. Starting from the decomposition, the equilibrium \mathbf{x}^* :

$$x_k^* = 1 + Z_k + R_k,$$

where $Z_k = \sum_{\ell=1}^n B_{k\ell}$, $\forall k \in [n]$ and we assume that $\forall k \in [n]$, R_k is a negligible term if n is sufficiently large.

The feasibility of the b communities is studied independently. Using Gaussian addition properties, a simpler form of Z_k is derived. Consider a family $(\check{Z}_k)_{k \in [n]}$ of i.i.d. random variables $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$.

$$\text{If } k \in \mathcal{I}_i, \quad Z_k = \sum_{j=1}^b \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{I}_j} B_{k\ell} \sim \sum_{j=1}^b \mathcal{N}(0, \beta_j s_{ij}^2) \sim \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^b \beta_j s_{ij}^2} \check{Z}_k.$$

Given $\beta = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_b)$, conditions on the matrix \mathbf{s} are inferred to have

$$\mathbb{P}(\min_{k \in [n]} x_k > 0) = 1 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \mathbb{P}(\min_{k \in [n]} Z_k > -1) = 1.$$

In order to compute a tractable form of $\min_{k \in [n]} Z_k$, an additional approximation is made, if n is large enough

$$(36) \quad \min_{k \in \mathcal{I}_i} \check{Z}_k \sim -\sqrt{2 \log(\beta_i n)} \simeq -\sqrt{2 \log(n)}.$$

With this approximation at hand, we can proceed:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{k \in [n]} Z_k &= \min_{i \in [b]} \left(\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^b \beta_j s_{ij}^2} \min_{k \in \mathcal{I}_i} \check{Z}_k \right) \simeq \min_{i \in [b]} \left(\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^b \beta_j s_{ij}^2} \left(-\sqrt{2 \log(n)} \right) \right) \\ &= \min_{i \in [b]} \left(-\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^b 2\beta_j s_{ij}^2 \log(n)} \right) = -\max_{i \in [b]} \left(\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^b 2\beta_j s_{ij}^2 \log(n)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Following the approximation (36), the condition $\min_{k \in [n]} Z_k > -1$ asymptotically boils down to

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{i \in [b]} \left(\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^b 2\beta_j s_{ij}^2 \log(n)} \right) < 1 &\Leftrightarrow \max_{i \in [b]} \left(\sum_{j=1}^b 2\beta_j s_{ij}^2 \log(n) \right) < 1, \\ &\Leftrightarrow \max_{i \in [b]} \left(\sum_{j=1}^b \beta_j s_{ij}^2 \right) < \frac{1}{2 \log(n)} \Leftrightarrow \|(\mathbf{s}_n \circ \mathbf{s}_n)^2 \beta^\top\|_\infty < \frac{1}{2 \log(n)} := (s_n^*)^2. \end{aligned}$$

□

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